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DEVELOPING A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY THROUGH THE USE OF SMART TECHNOLOGIES

The topic of this research is highly relevant in the context of the global transformations of the past decade. The rapid spread of SMART technologies — from artificial intelligence systems and the Internet of Things to platform-based resource management solutions — is fundamentally changing the operating logic of both individual enterprises and national economies as a whole. At the same time, challenges related to environmental pressure, energy consumption, and the need to transition to sustainable development models are intensifying, forcing entrepreneurs, government officials, and public figures to reconsider conventional approaches to economic activity.

The purpose of this study is to examine the conceptual interaction between SMART technologies and the principles of a sustainable economy, as well as to analyze statistical data characterizing key indicators: the level of digital solution adoption in production and management processes, dynamics of energy efficiency, carbon footprint, and economic performance of companies applying intelligent technologies. Particular attention is given to the role of artificial intelligence as a tool capable of ensuring not only operational efficiency, but also the long-term sustainability of business models.

The study is conceptual-analytical in nature and draws on a review of current academic literature, data from international organizations, and industry statistics. The findings may be of practical interest to decision-makers in the field of digital transformation and sustainable development.

Keywords: smart technologies, artificial intelligence, sustainability, sustainable economy, digital transformation, energy efficiency.

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The main current trends in sustainable development are aimed at developing a circular economy, which involves shifting the production and consumption paradigm from the principles of a traditional linear economy to a circular economy aimed at minimizing waste and resource depletion. Currently, the development of the global economy is impossible without the use of digital data, the Internet of Things, and artificial intelligence. Given the widespread use of technology in all activities, the connection between the level of technology use and sustainable economic development is becoming clear. To determine the impact of smart technology use on economic development, a conceptual analysis of the factors driving the formation of a circular economy and the use of smart technology in this regard was conducted. The primary objective of this study is to identify the relationship between the level of smart technology use and economic development. To achieve this goal, the following objectives were formulated: identify factors of sustainable economic development, identify how the use of smart technology influences these factors, and develop recommendations for implementing smart technology to achieve sustainable development. The study posed the following research question: How can smart technology influence sustainable economic development?

Given that the circular economy presupposes the protection of products and materials in use, the elimination of waste, and the careful use of natural systems, and smart technologies enable these goals to be achieved through digitalization, automation, and the development of predictive solutions based on analytics, a power effect between technologies and circularity emerges. The integration of smart technologies into the product lifecycle is noticeable at every stage, from the creation of digital twins, which allow for the modeling of a product's lifecycle and the determination of its environmental impact before production, to determining the feasibility of disassembly and recyclability. The use of sensors monitors energy and

resource consumption, identifies losses in real time, and optimizes equipment utilization, ultimately increasing the accuracy of the final product and, accordingly, reducing defects. The use of smart technologies at the global level is confirmed by the volume of the semiconductors which in 2025 was around 47,39 billion, but global sensor market size is forecasting 426 billion USD in 2030 [4].

The use of smart technologies also has a positive impact on optimizing supply chains at the local and global levels. Digital technologies create a unified information space that enables proactive responses to disruptions, as opposed to the traditional model's reactive incident management. Smart technologies enable accurate calculations in real time through predictive analytics and demand. Algorithms can analyze not only historical sales data but also external factors (holidays, weather forecasts, social trends, etc.), ultimately minimizing the likelihood of shortages or overstocking. Furthermore, the use of sensors and trackers that monitor not only the location of cargo but also transportation conditions allows for visibility into every stage of the product's journey, its safety, and the impact of external factors during transportation. In the context of logistics risk management, the use of digital twins allows for the creation of a virtual copy of the entire supply chain to simulate stress testing scenarios and determine action plans before emergencies arise. The use of autonomous mobile robots in warehouses makes the physical movement of goods faster and cheaper.

Another factor contributing to increased overall economic productivity and GDP growth is the reduction of labor costs, the reduction of equipment downtime through predictive analytics, and the acceleration of transaction processing through RPA. Smart technologies enable the automation of routine operations, while artificial intelligence and data processing help organizations make decisions based on forecasting through predictive analytics. At the same time, new business models, such as the platform economy, fintech solutions, and the sharing economy, are emerging. This, in turn, creates the foundation for innovative business models and, consequently, the emergence of new markets and the transformation of traditional industries. It's also worth noting the positive aspect of smart technologies, which accelerates the process of hypothesis testing and, ultimately, the implementation of innovations. The use of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and the Internet of Things, for example, enables the development of new medicines, the automation of logistics, and the creation of smart cities. Ultimately, this leads to the economy becoming globally competitive through the implementation of innovations. When analyzing changes in the structure of the labor market, it's impossible not to note both the positive and negative impacts. While the use of smart technologies creates new professions, it also limits low-skilled labor, leading to increased unemployment among this population group. This creates an urgent need for retraining and human capital development. This factor is confirmed by research conducted by Deloitte. The figure Most Common Talent Strategy Adjustments Due to Artificial Intelligence (AI) Worldwide in 2025 shows that the key focus of HR strategy adaptation is improving employees' overall AI literacy, as indicated by the highest share - 53%. This indicates a shift in organizations' focus from highly specialized skills to mass

training of personnel, which allows for increased business readiness for the implementation and effective use of AI technologies.

Figure. Most common talent strategy adjustments due to artificial intelligence (AI) worldwide in 2025

Source: Deloitte <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1659970/ai-impact-on-talent-strategy/>

At the same time, it's important to note the impact of smart technologies on sustainable development through reduced energy consumption, emissions management, optimized resource use, and the development of green technologies. This approach enables a transition to an environmentally oriented economy, which ultimately constitutes the principles of a circular economy.

To maximize the impact of smart technologies on economic development, it is necessary to formulate a strategic digital policy. This requires harmonizing national regulations and standards with international requirements, including those governing the use of artificial intelligence, personal data protection, and cybersecurity standards, industry adoption, and setting goals for the implementation of artificial intelligence and automation. At the same time, stimulating investment and innovation through the creation of innovation hubs and technology clusters, introducing tax incentives for the IT sector, and providing grants for technology implementation contributes to the development of an innovative environment for the

creation and implementation of smart technologies. It is also worth noting the recommendation for human capital development, which involves reforming educational programs with the integration of digital skills development. At the micro level, the creation of digital ecosystems is recommended, enabling data exchange, the use of collaborative platforms, and the integration of supply chains. The development of open platforms and an API economy, as well as standardization and interoperability, will facilitate integration between market participants to achieve a shared development effect. When implementing smart technologies, it is also necessary to consider emerging risks, which must be identified at an early stage. To this end, it is recommended to develop a risk management strategy, develop indicators to identify risks before reaching a set threshold, and move from detective to preventive risk analysis.

Thus, based on the above, the implementation of smart technologies demonstrably contributes to sustainable economic development by influencing its core components: from energy efficiency and resource optimization to more informed and transparent decision-making at both the enterprise and national levels. The effects are not limited to operational improvements; in a broader sense, SMART technologies reshape the very architecture of economic activity, making it more adaptive, measurable, and accountable.

However, it would be premature to assume that technological adoption alone is sufficient. The practical experience of both developed and developing economies shows that the benefits of smart technologies are neither automatic nor evenly distributed. Their realization depends heavily on the readiness of the institutional environment, the quality of infrastructure, the competence of human capital, and the coherence of regulatory frameworks. Where these conditions are underdeveloped, the risks - including data security vulnerabilities, growing digital inequality, and the displacement of labor, - can offset the anticipated gains.

Thus, based on the above, the implementation of smart technologies has a positive effect on ensuring sustainable economic development through its impact on various components. At the same time, it is necessary to develop a number of measures to ensure the proper integration of smart technologies in order to maximize benefits and minimize emerging risks.

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DEMOCRACY AND THE POLITICAL SYSTEM IN ROMANIA: EVIDENCE FROM THE EUROPEAN VALUES SURVEY

Introduction. The collapse of the communist bloc in 1989 marked the end of communist ideology and the entry of Central and Eastern European states onto the path of capitalist modernization. In Romania, the process of change has been constantly redefined in the last 36 years, giving rise to a society that oscillates between tradition and modernization.

The post-communist period in Romania is marked by a series of problems whose origins can be traced back to the communist period, to the economic, social and cultural policies promoted after World War II. One of the dilemmas that Romanian society faces is related to the different way generations born before and after 1989 relate to the multiparty political system in Romania and to the degree of trust that Romanian citizens have in Romanian democracy. The present study aims to analyze the way in which generations before and after 1989 relate to these problems.

The lack of multiparty system, a phenomenon characteristic of totalitarian societies, and not experiencing the „multiparty competition” directly influence the opinion on politics and democracy (Pop-Eleches and Tucker, 2014). For Romanians born during the communist period, the notion of a political party was identical to that of the communist party, that is, a single political formation that monopolized the entire political spectrum. The communist legacy has negatively influenced residents' perceptions of the political system in the countries of the former communist bloc. (Pop-Eleches and Tucker, 2011). Another analysis was conducted by Pop-Eleches and Tucker (2014) who analysed “the effect of individual exposure to [communism](#) on support for democracy and capitalism”. The population’s evaluation of democracy depends both on political and democratic knowledge and on democratic values in that country (Carsten Wegscheider and Toralf Stark, 2020). „The more authoritarian the regime, the more negative the evaluation of democratic performance by people who are more knowledgeable about democracy. In contrast, (...) the more democratic the regime, the more positive is the assessment of